

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

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STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

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Citation: Butler, L. A., Matthias, L., Simard, M. A., & Haustein, S. (2022). The Oligopoly's Shift to Open Access Publishing: How For-Profit Publishers Benefit from Gold and Hybrid Article Processing Charges. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti22112). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6951572>

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26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

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The Oligopoly’s Shift to Open Access Publishing: How For-Profit Publishers Benefit from Gold and Hybrid Article Processing Charges

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Introduction

While the growth in open access (OA) (Piwowar et al., 2018) can be seen as a positive development towards making research more accessible, OA is complicated and fraught by the academic publishing market, a profitable business controlled by an oligopoly of academic publishers, which consists of a few for-profit companies (Elsevier, SAGE, Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis, and Wiley). Since the beginning of the digital era, these companies have acquired small publishers and now control the majority of scholarly journal publishing (Larivière et al., 2015), generating profit margins as high as 37% (Aspesi et al., 2019). These profits stem largely from subscription fees and article processing charges (APCs) paid by the academic community to read and publish content provided for free by that same community.

While these publishing houses traditionally operate on subscription models — leading to the serials crisis and big deals that libraries could no longer afford (SPARC, 2020) — they increasingly offer various routes to OA publishing. The oligopoly often equates OA with the so-called author-pays model based on (often astronomic) APCs that create inequities and barriers that exclude many authors from publishing.

The majority of gold OA journals does not require authors to pay (10,988 out of 15,110 journals indexed in the DOAJ have no APCs) but high APCs are common from prestigious publishers (Khoo, 2019; Siler & Frenken, 2020). For gold OA journals that do rely on APCs, previous studies estimate the average fees to be \$1,800 (Jahn & Tullney, 2016; Solomon & Björk, 2016). Counterintuitively, hybrid APCs—subscription journals where individual articles are made freely available through APCs—are significantly more expensive (Pinfield et al., 2016; Matthias, 2018), with average estimates of \$2,900 (Jahn & Tullney, 2016; Solomon & Björk, 2016). Originally suggested as a transitional phase to flip subscription journals to OA (Björk, 2012; Draux et al., 2018, Prosser, 2003), the hybrid model was developed by publishers as a way to provide an OA option to authors of articles published in paid journals and to compete with the pressures of gold OA journals (Budzinski et al., 2020). The main criticisms of hybrid OA are the high price point with APCs and the potential for publishers to double-dip—the practice of receiving two different sources of revenue for the same article (Eve, 2014; Matthias, 2018; Pinfield et al., 2016; Suber, 2012).

This study aims to estimate the total cost of APCs obtained by oligopoly publishers between 2015 and 2018. More specifically, it aims to answer the following research question: What are the total costs (in USD) of APCs for gold and hybrid OA articles indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) associated with journals controlled by oligopoly publishers between 2015 and 2018?

Methods

This study combines data from WoS, Unpaywall, open datasets of APC list prices (Matthias, 2020; Morrison et al., 2021), as well as historical APC fees manually retrieved via the Internet Archive Wayback Machine. Peer-reviewed journal articles published by one of the oligopoly publishers between 2015 and 2018 were identified using WoS, with imprints and/or subsidiary publishing companies manually assigned to the parent oligopoly company. Document types were restricted to articles as these include original research findings and excludes document types (e.g., editorial material, reviews) that might be exempt from APCs. Publications were further restricted to include only those with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to retrieve their access status via Unpaywall.

The April 2020 snapshot of the Unpaywall.org database was used to obtain the OA status (gold, hybrid, bronze, green, closed) for each DOI in our dataset. This study focuses on hybrid and gold articles, as they are the ones potentially associated with APCs.

Annual APC list prices were determined for any journal that had at least one gold or hybrid article based on the WoS-Unpaywall dataset. For the majority of oligopoly journals, APCs were derived from an open dataset (Matthias, 2020), which include annual APCs in USD for Elsevier, SAGE, Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis, and Wiley journals. APC data was verified for completeness and several steps were taken to fill remaining gaps, including an extensive manual search of archived publisher's webpages on the Internet Wayback Machine. Data that could not be obtained from Matthias (2020) or the Wayback Machine was obtained from APCs collected by Morrison et al. (2021). Remaining gaps were filled by applying the fees from the closest year of existing APC data or current (2021/2022) prices.

Preliminary results

We estimate that the total of all gold and hybrid APCs for OA articles published in oligopoly journals indexed in WoS between 2015 and 2018 was \$US 1.3 billion, with annual amounts increasing from \$US 245 to \$US 395 million (Figure 1). Comparing publishers, we estimate that Springer-Nature obtained \$US 649, Elsevier \$US 454 million, Wiley \$US 126 million,

Taylor & Francis \$US 83 million and Sage \$US 35 million for gold and hybrid APCs from articles published in WoS-indexed journals during the 4-year period analyzed.

Figure 1: Total amount of APCs (gold & hybrid) per publisher per year.

Figure 2: Total amount of gold (A) and hybrid (B) APCs per publisher per year.

Differentiating between gold and hybrid APCs, we see that Springer-Nature (78% of APCs from gold vs. 22% from hybrid APCs), Sage (75% vs 25%) and Taylor & Francis (68% vs 32%) seem to focus more on gold OA, while Elsevier (13% vs 87%) and Wiley (39% vs 61%) heavily lean on hybrid OA (Figure 2). Average APCs per article were higher for hybrid (US\$ 2,909) than gold (US\$ 1,992 all gold; US\$ 2,216 gold w/ APC), corroborating findings from previous studies.

Discussion

The oligopoly's revenues from gold and hybrid APCs continue to increase, demonstrating a strong source of profits at the cost of authors, and like previous studies demonstrate, their control of the scholarly publishing market (Larivière et al., 2015). Instead of making scholarly publishing sustainable and accessible for all, exorbitant APCs (and more recently transformative agreements) preserve the status quo of the academic publishing market. The author-pays model excludes large parts of the academic community from publishing, giving preference to well-funded authors, disciplines and countries (Olejniczak & Wilson, 2020). Instead of removing barriers from academic publishing, OA APCs have shifted inequities from readers to authors, often affecting those same individuals (Simard et al., 2021).

Outlook

Further analyses will include breakdowns by discipline, country of corresponding authors, journal and acknowledged funders to provide empirical evidence about the inequities and the unsustainability of the current author-pays route to OA.

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